

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part XVII

Two Configurational Isomers of 3,4-Dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic Acid

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1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid has been prepared by condensing 3,4-dimethylcyclohexanone with ethyl cyanoacetate employing Cope's method to give ethyl 3,4-dimethylcyclohexylidene cyanoacetate and subsequent reaction with ethanolic potassium cyanide followed by hydrolysis. This acid has been separated into two isomers and configurations assigned; each of the isomers has by a series of reactions been degraded to the corresponding 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acid.

THE preparation and assignment of configurations to the two isomeric forms of 4-, 3- and 2-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids, being trisubstituted derivatives of cyclohexane, have been reported by Bajaj, Desai and Saharia¹. Perusal of literature revealed that barring the work on the preparation of 1-carboxy 3,3- and 4,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid^{2,3} hardly any analogous work on the tetrasubstituted derivatives of cyclohexane has been reported. The present communication describes the synthesis of isomeric 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids and their conversion to the corresponding 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids.

3,4-Dimethylcyclohexanone required for the work was obtained by the catalytic reduction of the corresponding xlenol followed by oxidation which predominantly (97.6%) possesses the cis-configuration.⁴

the first method, 3,4-dimethylcyclohexanone has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate following Cope's method⁵ and the unsaturated ester so obtained on reaction with ethanolic potassium cyanide followed by hydrolysis furnished 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (I) as a mixture of two acids having m.p. 105-28°. While in the other, the condensation of 1-hydroxy-1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate was carried out to give 1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate. This dicyanoester on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished the acid (I), m.p. 105-27°. This acid has been separated into two isomers A, m.p. 181° and B, m.p. 160° by fractional crystallisation from ethyl acetate-pet. ether and benzene-pet. ether which were obtained in the ratio of 1 : 3.

In order to assign configurations to the two isomers, each was converted into its ethyl ester and their

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid has been synthesized by two different routes and in

b.ps and refractive indices recorded. Out of the two groups $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{COOH}$ in I at C_1 , the

former being bulkier would occupy the equatorial position in the chair conformation. As a consequence of this four different configurations of the acid I could be represented by II (a, b, c and d; R = H) depending upon whether one or both the methyl groups occupy equatorial or axial positions.

Configuration IIa would be energetically the most favourable and thus stable for both the methyl groups are in equatorial positions as the molecule would be free from any 1,3-diaxial interactions. On the other hand IIc will be most unstable because of 1,3-hydrogen-methyl and 1,3-methyl-carboxyl interactions and therefore, this could be ruled out.

Out of the remaining two configurations, IIb and IIc, the latter would distinctly possess higher energy since the methyl group at C-3 and -COOH group at C-1 occupy axial positions and appear on the same side of the ring. Thus, the order of the relative stabilities of the different configurations would be in the order, $a > b > c > d$ and the two isomers A and B could be considered to have the configurations a and b.

On the basis of von Auwers-Skita rule as modified by Allinger⁶ the isomer A (refractive index of the ethyl ester, n_D^{25} 1.4665) is assigned the structure 'a' in which both the methyl groups assume equatorial positions and the isomer B (refractive index of the ethyl ester, n_D^{25} 1.4785) is assigned the structure 'b' in which the methyl groups at C-3 and C-4 assume equatorial and axial positions respectively.

von Auwers-Skita rule in the case of b.p.s of the ethyl esters of isomers Ia and Ib (b.p.s Ia—130-1°/1.5 mm; Ib—111°/2 mm) was found to be reversed in accordance with that reported by Eliel and Haber⁷ in the case of isomeric methylcyclohexanols, also suggested by van Bekkum and others⁸ that the conformational rule should be confined to density and refractive index, since the rule frequently fails for b.p.

Further, assignment of structure 'b' in preference to 'c' for the isomer B is supported by the observations of Noyce and Dolly⁴ that the major transition state contributor in the lithium aluminium hydride reduction of cis-3,4-dimethylcyclohexanone has 3e, 4a dimethyl configuration.

The configurations assigned receive further support from the nmr spectra of the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid A, m.p. 181° in $CDCl_3$ which gave an intense signal at 0.97 δ arising from six methyl protons. Whereas the nmr spectra of the anhydride of the acid B, m.p. 160° showed two signals at 1.03 δ and 0.9 δ due to methyl protons because axial and equatorial methyl protons absorb at different fields⁹.

The isomeric 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids (IIa and IIb; R = H) were degraded to the respective -1,1-dicarboxylic acids according to the procedure of Desai, Hunter and Saharia^{1,10}. It was observed that addition of traces of red phosphorus to the brominating mixture already having a crystal of iodine, facilitated the completion of the

reaction (2 hours). It may be mentioned that no neutral product was isolated contrary to the early observations^{1,10} and it may be probable that prolonged heating for a longer time resulted in the formation of the neutral product.

The yields of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1- α -bromoacetic acids (IIa and IIb; R = Br) were quantitative and those of the corresponding hydroxy acids (IIa and IIb; R = OH) ranged between 76 to 79%. The structures of the bromo acids and the glycolic acids were confirmed by analytical data, eq. weight determination and I.R. spectral data. The glycolic acids were later oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate to the respective 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids (IIIa and IIIb) in yields of 47-55%. These acids solidified only on keeping in vacuum for over two months followed by trituration with benzene and pet. ether.

Our results regarding the structures of glycolic acids and -1,1-dicarboxylic acids, are in consonance with the observations of Bajaj *et al.*¹, Desai *et al.*¹⁰ thereby further contradicting the claims made by Price and co-workers¹¹.

Experimental

(a) Ethyl 3,4-dimethylcyclohexylidene cyanoacetate

A mixture of 3,4-dimethylcyclohexanone (63 g; 0.5 mole), ethyl cyanoacetate (56.5 g; 0.5 mole), ammonium acetate (4.0 g; 0.05 mole), glacial acetic acid (6.0 g; 0.1 mole) and dry benzene (120 ml) contained in a R.B. flask (500 ml) fitted with a modified Dean and Stark water separator, in turn connected to a reflux condenser, was heated in an oil bath at 120-60°. Water separated out of the mixture was drawn off at intervals and the mixture refluxed for an additional period of two hours after the separation of water had stopped (3 hours). The benzene solution was cooled, washed with water (2 $\times$ 100 ml) and the washings were extracted with benzene (40 ml). The combined benzene extracts after drying and removal of benzene gave ethyl 3,4-dimethylcyclohexylidene cyanoacetate, b.p. 160-3°/8-9 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4735. (Yield : 89.6%). (Found : C, 70.5; H, 8.5. $C_{19}H_{29}O_2N$ requires C, 70.6; H, 8.6%). I.R. ν_{max}^{film} 1720 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ (α , β -unsaturated ester); 1600 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = C$, 2250 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C \equiv N$, λ_{max} 235 μ .

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (I)

To the solution of ethyl 3,4-dimethylcyclohexylidene cyanoacetate (99.9 g; 0.43 mole) in rectified spirit was gradually added potassium cyanide (58.5 g; 0.9 mole) in water (100 ml) with shaking and cooling, and the contents left at room temperature for 96 hrs. Alcohol was distilled off at the pump, the residue cooled and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid when an oily layer separated out. This was extracted with ether and the residue after the removal of ether was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (200 ml) on a sand bath for 90 hrs; a semi-solid product which had settled down was separated by decantation and washed with water. This was dissolved in aq. sodium hydroxide (10%) and heated under reflux until the evolution of ammonia had ceased (15 hrs.)

and the alkaline solution on acidification deposited an oil which solidified after keeping at room temperature for four days and had m.p. 105–27°. (Yield : 81%).

(b) *Synthesis of 1-hydroxy-1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane*

To a mixture of 3,4-dimethylcyclohexanone (32 g; 0.25 mole) and potassium cyanide (16.3 g; 0.25 mole) in water (100 ml) was slowly added, with stirring, dilute sulphuric acid (167 g; 30% by weight) and temperature maintained below 20°. After two hours, the contents were extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the solvent removed, the residue on distillation with two drops of conc. sulphuric acid gave 1-hydroxy-1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane, b.p. 129°–30°/5–6 mm. n_D^{20} 1.4570. (Yield : 73%). (Found : C, 70.3; H, 9.7. $C_9H_{15}ON$ requires C, 70.5; H, 9.8%). I.R. ν_{max}^{film} 2265 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C \equiv N$; 3605 cm^{-1} ; $\nu O-H$ (alcoholic monomeric).

Ethyl 1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate

1-Hydroxy-1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane (22.9 g; 0.15 mole) was slowly added, with cooling and stirring, to the sodio derivative of ethyl cyanoacetate prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (16.95 g; 0.15 mole) by the action of sodium ethoxide (sodium 3.45 g; 0.15 mole and absolute alcohol 55 ml). The mixture after keeping at room temperature for 24 hrs. was diluted with water and acidified when an oily layer separated out. After working up in the normal manner, pure 1-cyano-3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate had b.p. 160°/5 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4696. (Yield : 61.6%). (Found : C, 67.5; H, 8.0. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires C, 67.7; H, 8.1%). I.R. ν_{max}^{film} 2260 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C \equiv N$; 1730 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of ester.

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (I)

Ethyl 1-cyano 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate (20 g) was hydrolysed with conc. hydrochloric acid as described earlier and the crude acid had m.p. 105–28°. (Yield : 83.1%).

Separation of isomeric 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids

The above acid 70 (g) was finely powdered and refluxed with petrol (60°–80°) containing a small quantity of benzene for an hour, the residue m.p. 167–75° on further treatment with benzene and crystallisation from ethyl acetate-benzene gave 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, (IIa) as thick clusters of white needles m.p. 181°. (Found : C, 61.6; H, 8.3; equiv., 106.8. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.7; H, 8.4%; equiv. 107.0—dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{solid} 1710 cm^{-1} . Anhydride, m.p. 104.5°, Anilic acid, m.p. 165°, *p*-Tolylamic acid, m.p. 185°, *p*-Chloroanilic acid, m.p. 178°, *m*-Nitroanilic acid, m.p. 178°.

The petrol and benzene mother liquors were combined, concentrated to half its total volume and on standing deposited a solid m.p. 140–7°. This on treatment with benzene gave a residue melting at 173–5° which on repeated crystallisations gave

more quantity of acid IIa. The final mother liquor on further concentration deposited a fraction melting at 153–7°; on two crystallisations from benzene, 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, IIb was obtained in white cubes and had m.p. 160°. (Found : C, 61.5; H, 8.4; equiv., 106.7. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.7; H, 8.4%; equiv., 107.0—dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{solid} 1705 cm^{-1} . Anhydride, b.p. 183–4°/10–11 mm., Anilic acid, m.p. 160°, *p*-Tolylamic acid, m.p. 193°, *m*-Nitroanilic acid, m.p. 168°. Mixed m.p. of the acid IIa, m.p. 181° with the acid Ib, m.p. 160° in the ratio 2 : 1 was depressed to 142–6°.

Bromination of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid IIa, m.p. 180° (IIa, R = Br)

Powdered phosphorus pentachloride (11.5 g; 0.055 mole) and 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (5.35 g; 0.025 mole) were mixed together and the mixture heated under reflux for 6 hrs. Bromine (5.73 g; 0.0275 mole) was added to the cooled contents during two hours and left overnight at room temperature with a crystal of iodine and a pinch of red phosphorus. After exposing the contents to U.V. light for 6 hrs, the reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath at 55–60° for 24 hrs. and poured into anhydrous formic acid (98%; 50 ml) with constant stirring. After the initial reaction had subsided, the contents were heated on a water bath until the decomposition was complete (2 hrs.). The solid which separated out after keeping overnight, was filtered, washed with petrol and on crystallisation from benzene-petrol (40–50°) 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1- α -bromoacetic acid was obtained in white cubes and had m.p. 149°. (Yield : 81.9%). (Found : C, 45.0; H, 5.6; Br, 27.2; equiv., 146.1. $C_{11}H_{17}O_4Br$ requires C, 45.1; H, 5.8; Br, 27.3; equiv., 146.5—dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{solid} 1700 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of acid and 1720 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of α -halogenated acid.

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid (IIa; R = OH)

The above α -bromo acid (5 g) was neutralized with aqueous sodium carbonate (2N) and the solution refluxed on a sand bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The residue, after the removal of ether, on trituration with petrol (60–80°) containing a few drops of benzene gave a colourless solid melting at 152–5°. This was crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (60°–80°) in white plates and pure 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid had m.p. 158°. (Yield : 78.9%). (Found : C, 57.1; H, 7.7; equiv. 114.8. $C_{11}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 57.4; H, 7.8%; 115.0 dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{solid} 1705 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of acid; 3625 cm^{-1} ; $\nu O-H$.

3,4-Dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acid (IIIa)

The solution of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid (2.3 g) in water was neutralised with aqueous barium hydroxide (N/20) and potassium permanganate (4.5 g in water, 450 ml) was slowly added during 5 hrs. while the mixture kept constantly stirred. The contents were allowed to stand at room

temperature for 15 hrs, and the unreacted permanganate was destroyed by passing sulphur dioxide. The pptd manganese dioxide was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk, the alkaline solution acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid, saturated with ammonium sulphate and continuously extracted with ether for 10 hrs. The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, ether recovered and the residue kept in vacuum for two months; on trituration with benzene-petrol (60–80°) a colourless solid, m.p. 150–2° was obtained. On crystallisation from ethyl acetate petrol (60–80°), 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 155° was obtained in colourless cubes. (Yield : 55%). (Found : C, 59.8; H, 7.9; equiv., 99.7; $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0%; equiv., 100.0—dibasic). Mixed m.p. with 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid IIa, m.p. 181° in the ratio 1 : 1 was depressed to 130–40° and with the acid IIb, m.p. 160° was depressed to 141–3°. I.R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1715 cm^{-1} . Its diethyl ester distilled at 132/3 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4410.

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1- α -bromo acetic acid (IIb; R = Br) prepared in the manner followed in the case of isomer IIa had m.p. 146–7° (Yield : 84.6%). (Found : C, 45.0; H, 5.5; Br, 27.1%; equiv., 145.9. $C_{11}H_{17}O_4Br$, requires C, 45.1; H, 5.8; Br, 27.3%; equiv., 146.5—dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1700 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of acid; 1715 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of α -halogenated acid.

1-Carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid (IIb; R = OH) had m.p. 152–3°. (Yield : 76.1%). (Found : C, 57.2; H, 7.5; equiv., 114.6. $C_{11}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 57.4; H, 7.8%; equiv., 115.0—dibasic). I.R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1707 cm^{-1} ; $\nu C = O$ of acid; 3630 cm^{-1} ; $\nu O-H$.

3,4-Dimethyl cyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acid (IIIb) m.p. 172° was prepared following the method adopted as for the isomer IIIa. (Yield : 47.5%). (Found : 59.7; H, 8.0; equiv., 99.7. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0%; 100.0—dibasic). Mixed m.p. with 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid IIb, m.p. 160° in the ratio of 1 : 1 was depressed to 145–50°, while the mixed IIIa m.p. with 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acid, IIIa m.p. 155° in the ratio of 2 : 1 was depressed to 140–7°. I.R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1721 cm^{-1} . Its diethyl ester distilled at 115°/4 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4525.

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